

☞ CIEEL: A Continuous Integration Framework for Exams and Exercise Lists

Mateus Molina

University of Kaiserslautern-Landau
Kaiserslautern, Germany
mateus.molina@rptu.de

Abstract—Managing large-scale exam and exercise list production in university courses is a recurring, error-prone task. Typical problems include stale questions that remain uncorrected, conceptual distribution shift between exercise lists and exams, and undiscovered errors that surface only during assessment. We present CIEEL (Continuous Integration for Exams and Exercise Lists), a lightweight framework and toolset that applies software engineering practices—namely version control, modular component design, and issue tracking—to the lifecycle of academic assessments. Built on \LaTeX and structured around a shared, uniquely identified question pool, CIEEL enables instructors to compose exams and exercise lists from reusable variant components, track quality issues per question, and progressively improve assessment material across semesters. We describe the framework’s architecture, its \LaTeX implementation, and the workflow activities that support collaborative contribution of new variants. An open example repository is provided for adoption.

Index Terms—assessment engineering, exam management, LaTeX tooling, question pool, continuous integration

I. INTRODUCTION

Producing high-quality exams and exercise lists (ELs) at scale is a non-trivial software engineering problem. Courses with hundreds of students demand rigorous quality control, yet typical academic workflows lack the systematic tooling that software teams take for granted.

Through our experience coordinating several lectures with up to 300 students each, we identified three recurring challenges:

Challenge 1 (Staleness). Questions accumulate defects (ambiguous wording, outdated references, flawed scoring) with no per-question tracking, so issues persist across semesters.

Challenge 2 (Distribution Shift). Exam and EL question pools drift conceptually, so students encounter exam questions on under-practiced topics.

Challenge 3 (Fault Detection). New variants authored without peer review may harbor undetected errors that surface during the exam, forcing last-minute scoring adjustments.

II. RELATED WORK

In our experience, the prevalent workflow is *copy-and-edit*: a new per-semester directory is created, files from the previous semester are copied in, and questions are manually revised. ELs and exams operate often in distinct question pools; corrections are never propagated back to a shared

Fig. 1. ☞ CIEEL workflow. Dashed arrows represent dependency, while solid arrows represent data flow.

source, and accumulated feedback is lost between iterations. Modularizing questions with \LaTeX is challenging, leading to question management being realized by copying and modifying entire question files, which leads to maintenance issues and error propagation. Therefore, some actors opt to author questions in a thin wrapper on top of \LaTeX or custom DSL [1], however this adds another coupling point and learning curve, and often breaks down when novel question types or formatting are required. The closest solution is provided by `r/exams` [2], addressing mostly Challenge 2.

☞ CIEEL tackles Challenges 1 to 3 and provides a structured workflow for collaborative question management, while staying lightweight by relying on \LaTeX for authoring.

III. THE ☞ CIEEL FRAMEWORK

The core abstraction is the *Questions Pool*: a version-controlled repository of uniquely identified *variants*. A *question* groups semantically related variants that target the same concept from different perspectives (e.g., varying input parameters, problem framing, or domain context). Variants within a question must be (i) thematically consistent, and (ii) structurally similar but focusing on distinct aspects of the concept.

Four activities operate on the pool (Fig. 1):

Activity A1 (Contribute New Variants). Team members propose variants via merge requests; mandatory peer review acts as a pre-release gate (Challenge 3).

Activity A2 (Generate New Exam). The instructor selects pool variants and authors new ones; after grading, new variants are contributed back (Challenge 2).

Activity A3 (Generate New EL). An EL is assembled from pool variants covering the scheduled lecture concepts; new

Fig. 2. CIEEL \LaTeX package dependency graph.

variants are contributed back analogously to exams (Challenge 2).

Activity A4 (Raise Issues). Contributors open issues against a variant’s unique path to capture defects; issues persist until resolved via merge request, creating a per-question defect log across semesters (Challenge 1).

IV. SEDA-FLAVORED CIEEL

A. Package Architecture

Our flavor of CIEEL relies on \LaTeX extensively, due to its ubiquity in academia, its powerful macro system for defining reusable components, and its native support for complex mathematical notation and formatting.

The tooling layer consists of three \LaTeX packages (Fig. 2): `cieel-core.sty` provides shared utilities; `cieel-exam.sty` and `cieel-exercises.sty` extend it for exams and ELs, respectively. Variants are authored using the standard exam document class [3] and stored under `questions/{question}/{variant}.tex`.

B. Composing an Exam or Exercise List

An exam or EL document reduces to a list of `\registerQuestion` calls:

```
\include{cieel-exam.sty}
\documentclass{exam}

\registerQuestion{questions/topic1/var1}
\registerQuestion{questions/topic2/var3}

\begin{document}
\printQuestions
\end{document}
```

Listing 1. Minimal exam definition.

`\registerQuestion{PATH}` resolves the variant, loads its local `requirements.sty` on demand, and registers its asset path—making variants self-contained and reusable without dependency or path conflicts.

C. Variant Structure

A minimal variant follows the exam class convention:

```
% METADATA
\question This question tests concept X.
\begin{parts}
  \part[4] Sub-question 1...
  \part[4] Sub-question 2...
\end{parts}
```

Listing 2. Variant template.

We recommend a structured metadata comment block at the top of each variant file to tag, comment, specify data and add author information. This information can be used for automated analysis and selection of variants.

Points are assigned using a time-calibrated scale where 1 pt \approx 1 min of expected completion time, validated empirically at the start of each semester. Variants are constrained to 8–16 pt to maintain consistent cognitive load and scheduling predictability.

D. Quality Feedback Loop

The issue tracker is the connective element between assessment delivery and pool improvement. Issues filed via Activity A4 are resolved by the same merge-request workflow used in Activity A1, so every fix is peer-reviewed before it reaches students. Fault detection (Challenge 3) is addressed upstream at authoring time through that same peer-review gate, while staleness (Challenge 1) is addressed downstream through the issue log. Additionally a CI pipeline can be set up that compiles all variants and exams on every commit, ensuring that any introduced compilation errors are caught immediately.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

CIEEL demonstrates that software engineering practices, i.e., modular components, version control, issue tracking, and code review, transfer naturally to academic assessment management. The framework’s modest requirements (\LaTeX and a git-hosted repository) lower the adoption barrier for existing courses.

Key benefits include: reduced question staleness through per-variant issue tracking; improved exam–EL alignment via a shared pool; and lower exam error rates due to the quality feedback loop.

An open example repository demonstrating the framework is available at <https://github.com/mateusmolina/cieel>.

REFERENCES

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